

**DEVELOPMENT OF A LOW-COST ENVIRONMENTAL DEVICE FOR AIR QUALITY
MONITORING**

BY

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Certification

This is to certify that the project work titled “DEVELOPMENT OF A LOW-COST ENVIRONMENTAL DEVICE FOR AIR QUALITY MONITORING” was carried out by OGUNSESAN OLAMIDE LATEEF, with Matriculation Number MEE/2017/0018, of Mechanical Engineering department, Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State.

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Dedication

I dedicate this Project to God almighty and to everyone who helped us in one way or the other by contributing to the success of this program. I say a massive thank you, and may God continue to be with us.

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First and foremost, our deepest gratitude goes to Almighty God for the gift of life. His continuous guidance, direction and protection throughout our study period for this degree.

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ABSTRACT

Pollutants are toxic solids, liquids, or gases created in higher-than-normal concentrations that degrade our environment. Air pollution is a major problem in Nigeria. There is a lack of existing data on the pollutant type and pollution level in most areas. The availability of a low-cost air quality monitor will simplify air quality forecasting with the overall goal of safeguarding the public and environmental health. This study was carried out with the aim to develop a low-cost environmental device for air quality monitoring device to detect PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and Volatile Organic Compounds, assess the performance of the developed monitor and compare the cost of the device with the available Industrial-Made device. The developed device was deployed to the study areas which are a motor park, a busy road intersection and a market, all in Osogbo with an industrial made device in order to compare the performance of the two devices. Graphs are plotted, toxicity potential and air quality index are calculated from the data obtained for the particulate matter being studied. This was later used to assess and compare the performance of the developed and the industrial made device.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The environment is as old as the concept of nature itself. It is a broad phrase that refers to the conditions in which organisms made up of air, water, food, sunlight, and other elements thrive and serve as living sources of life for all living and non-living creatures, including plants. Temperature, wind, and velocity are also included in the word. (Reddy *et al.*, 2017). As a result of diverse human activities influencing the environment, the interactions between humans and their physical surroundings are intensively explored. The biotic (living beings and microbes) and abiotic (insensible objects) worlds collide in the surroundings (hydrosphere, lithosphere, and atmosphere). (Manisalidis *et al.*, 2020).

Pollution is any human action that causes the natural environment's quality to deteriorate or degrade. Environmental pollution is not a new occurrence, yet it remains humanity's greatest burden and one of the leading causes of environmental diseases and deaths. In 2015, pollution was projected to have caused 9 million premature deaths, more than three times the number of deaths caused by malaria, AIDS, and tuberculosis. (Ukaogo *et al.*, 2020). The benefits of modern urban, industrial, economic, and technological development are numerous. However, industrial air and water pollution, uncontrolled deforestation and conversion of forest land to agricultural land, destruction of the ozone layer, the accumulation of various wastes, including radioactive wastes, and the extinction of certain plant and animal species are just a few of the negative consequences of human activities that endanger the environment. (Bećirović, 2015).

Pollutants are toxic solids, liquids, or gases created in higher-than-normal concentrations that degrade our environment. (Manisalidis *et al.*, 2020). Air pollution is the emission of pollutants into the atmosphere that are harmful to human health and the environment. The quality of the air is degrading daily. The United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has designated six pollutants as "criteria" air pollutants because it controls them by defining human health- and environmental-based criteria (science-based guidelines) for determining permitted levels. Carbon monoxide (CO), lead (Pb), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ground-level ozone, particle pollution (also known as particulate matter), and sulfur oxides are the six pollutants mentioned (SO_x). These pollutants come from various sources, including automobile emissions, energy generation, industrial operations, residential combustion systems, fossil-fuel combustion, forest fires, metal processing, agricultural waste incineration, construction sites, etc.

Air pollution has an impact on both humans and animals. Cough, shortness of breath, wheezing, asthma, respiratory illness, and increased hospitalization rates are all associated with short-term air pollution exposure (measurement of morbidity). The long-term effects of air pollution are associated with chronic asthma, pulmonary insufficiency, cardiovascular diseases, and cardiovascular death. (Manisalidis *et al.*, 2020). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), air pollution kills over seven million people worldwide. Due to ambient air pollution, stroke, heart disease, lung cancer, and chronic respiratory disorders account for 4.2 million fatalities. Approximately 91 percent of the world's population lives in areas where air quality exceeds WHO guidelines. While both rich and developing nations are affected by ambient air pollution, low- and middle-income countries bear the brunt of the load, with the Eastern Pacific and Southeast Asia areas bearing the brunt of the toll. Each year, 3.8 million people die prematurely due to exposure to smoke from cooking fires, most of whom are from low- and

middle-income nations. Inefficient stoves or open hearths emit several health-damaging pollutants, including particulate matter (PM), methane, carbon monoxide, polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), and volatile organic compounds (VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDSs) (WHO, 2022).

Many different contaminants can have an impact on air quality. However, for most air quality measurements, several categories are utilized. Particles are a crucial consideration in almost every circumstance. One of the most difficult aspects of air quality management (QAM) is having timely and adequate access to relevant, high-quality data. Air quality monitoring provides the information needed to determine compliance with current ambient air quality norms and regulations and changes in pollutant concentrations. Most modern nations have some form of air quality monitoring in place in various areas, ranging in sophistication and quality assurance. Because air quality patterns change at various geographical and temporal dimensions, data collected from such sites may not accurately reflect pollution levels in other parts of the city. Because there are so many different techniques to air quality monitoring, there are still significant discrepancies in methodology, site selection, frequency, and dependability (quality assurance/quality control) of air quality and air quality standards monitoring. Because of these distinctions, air quality measurements and trends in one city cannot be directly compared to those in other locations within the same country.

Due to several factors, including the high cost of the monitors and their standard parts, for monitoring the pollutants in question, the scarcity of sensors, also the fact that the sensors have to be imported from outside the country, and the lack of data from the National Bureau of Statistics on the pollutants in question, namely nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS), this has resulted in the use of costly

equipment as well as the inability to build one promptly, resulting in a lack of needed data on the contamination of the two pollutants under consideration. The current study intends to create an environmental monitor using gas sensors that can detect both NO_x and VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS in the environment to address these concerns.

The atmosphere is the gaseous envelope that surrounds the earth and constitutes the transition between its surface and the vacuum of space (Bhatia, 2019). The atmosphere is composed primarily of nitrogen (N₂) and oxygen (O₂). It comprises many layers of air, each one of which is identified by its thermal characteristics or temperature changes, chemical composition, movement and density (Narayanan, 2019). Life on earth is supported by the layers of air, solar energy and our planet's magnetic fields, and the quality is essential to its sustenance (Oxlade, 2016; Ojo and Awokola, 2012). Air pollution is the introduction of chemicals, particulate matter or biological materials that cause harm and discomfort to humans and other living organisms (Bhatia, 2019). The most common air pollutants in the urban environment include Sulphur dioxide (SO₂); oxides of nitrogen (NO_x), such as nitrogen oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂); carbon monoxide (CO); volatile organic compounds (VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS); ozone (O₃); suspended particulate matter (SPM) also called particulates; and lead (Pb) (Lutgens and Edward, 2021). Air pollutants can be in the form of solid particles, liquid droplets, or gases. In addition, they may be natural or artificial (USEPA, 2006; Narayanan, 2019). Sources of air pollution include traffic (vehicle exhaust), industrial sectors (from brick making to oil and gas production), power plants and generating sets, cooking and heating with solid fuels (e.g., coal, wood, crop waste), forest fires and open burning of municipal waste and agricultural residues (Akanni, 2018; Komolafe *et al.*, 2014). Air pollution is becoming a topic of intense research because of increased anthropogenic activities and climatic changes. Air

pollution in the urban center has increased rapidly due to high population density, increased numbers of motor vehicles, use of fuels with poor environmental performance, poorly maintained transportation systems and, above all, ineffective environmental regulations and policies (Komolafe *et al.*, 2014). Air pollution is believed to kill more people worldwide than AIDS, malaria, breast cancer, or tuberculosis (WHO, 2014). Airborne particulate matter (PM) is especially detrimental to health (Beelen *et al.*, 2013). It has previously been estimated to cause between 3 and 7 million deaths every year, primarily by creating or worsening cardio-respiratory disease (Hoek *et al.*, 2013). Particulate sources include electric power plants, industrial facilities, automobiles, biomass burning, and fossil fuels used in homes and factories for heating. In China, air pollution was previously estimated to contribute to 1.2 to 2 million deaths annually (WHO, 2014; Yang *et al.*, 2013).

Accordingly, Ekuri and Eze (2020) defined pollution as "a contamination, a defilement, mischief, perturbation, and reduction in an object or thing". Relatedly, Jande (2005) describes the term – Pollution" to mean "to make something dirty or no longer pure, especially by adding harmful or unpleasant substances to it". In these findings, therefore, the concept "Pollution" refers to a situation where waste-materials and harmful substances which can deplete, wear/tear away and affect the entire environment and cause disorderliness to all living organisms. Air pollution is the presence of extra unwanted biological molecules, particulates, or other harmful things in the earth's atmosphere. It is a major cause of infections and allergies and eventually reasons of death for some people. (Abdullah *et al.*, 2018).

Air pollution is the presence of extra unwanted biological molecules, particulates or other harmful things in the earth's atmosphere. It is a major cause of infections and allergies and eventually reasons of death for some people. It also harms other creatures like animals and food

crops or the ecological or built environment. They are also accountable for various kinds of respiratory infections (like asthma) and causes of different types of cancer in individuals if they are unprotected from these toxins or chemicals for a long period. For example, carbon monoxide (CO) is extremely poisonous to people. It may happen serious asphyxiation and headaches because of the composition of carboxy-hemoglobin and thus a reason for death if unprotected for a long time. The world health organization (WHO) in 2014 approximated that 7 million people die worldwide because of air pollution. The International Energy Agency (IEA) roughly equaled a similar approximation. These chemicals or pollutants are also responsible for various environmental calamities like acid rain and depletion of the ozone layer. Because of several anthropogenic actions, air pollution is on the growth, and its controlling is of significant importance to alleviate particular actions to limit it. The air quality measuring sensors are very big, non-portable and expensive. Most air pollution sensors are currently developed on the five most common air pollutants: nitrous oxide, carbon monoxide, ozone, sulfur dioxide, and particulate matter. Air pollution and quality monitoring are vital in today's world as they greatly affect human health. The developed air-quality measurement sensor can identify and observe the incidence of air pollution in the adjacent areas. It can be employed both indoors and outdoors. With the help of future technological improvements, these sensors will become cheaper and more common, inexpensive, portable air-quality sensors that people can wear to observe the local air quality. In the Modern era, environmental issues have significantly impacted human life. Air pollution indoor and outdoor environment is sometimes dangerous to human health, and it needs to be justified.

1.2 Problem Statement

Air pollution is a major problem in Nigeria. There is a lack of existing data on the pollutant type and pollution level in most areas. Furthermore, in areas where such measurements are available, data collection is often done physically by a human subject entering the polluted site with hand-held measuring units, thereby exposing such individuals to health hazards. The measurement can also be time-consuming and monotonous, leading to boredom and data falsification. The availability of a low-cost air quality monitor will simplify air quality forecasting with the overall goal of safeguarding the public and environmental health, hence this study.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

This study aims to develop a low-cost environmental device for air quality monitors.

The objectives are to:

- i. develop a low-cost air quality monitoring device to detect PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and Volatile Organic Compounds with.
- ii. assess the performance of the developed monitor.
- iii. Compare the cost of the device with the available Industrial-Made device.

1.4 Research Justification

This study will provide a system to make air pollution data collection and monitoring easier in Nigeria. This will reduce the health hazards involved during measurements. Crucial data that will improve planning for the environment and the general public's health will also be made available from this study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

Nathaniel and Miaoli (2020) focused on assessing the health risk of particulate matter (PM) inhalation within Nigeria's Abuja municipal area. Particulate matters ($PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}), HCHO, and VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDSs are collected by A hand-held portable smart air quality detector BR-SMART-126. A hybrid single-particle Lagrangean integrated trajectory (HYSPLIT) model for backward trajectory was applied to tract the airflow (transportation) and potential sources. The health risk was estimated by comparing it with the air quality index (AQI) stipulated by the World Health Organization (WHO). The result shows that the daily averaged concentrations of $PM_{2.5}$ varied from $15.30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $70.20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The top four most-polluted locations (Locations 10, 14, 17, and 18) of the tiny locations are above the acceptable ($25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) AQI limit stipulated by WHO and fell far under the unhealthy AQI value index level. Business/commercial locations had the highest $PM_{2.5}$ level, followed by transport/market, offices/mixed-use, and residential. The backward trajectories show that the source of local particles for the four most-polluted locations is long-range air transport originating from the Atlantic Ocean. The results of the health-risk assessment imply that for $PM_{2.5}$, the AQI varied from 73.2 to 280.8 in this assessment. Based on this, the population of workers within the business location is a health risk based on the relatively poor air quality in these areas—especially locations 10 and 17. Based on these findings, it is recommended that the regulatory and enforcement agency needs to develop a more robust monitoring mechanism, regulations, and

enforcement. Furthermore, there is a need for a national drive on renewable energy and clean energy for business/commercial districts to help reduce fumes from generators and form cleaner air initiatives to ensure a safe environment to live in and reduce particulate matters in the city.

Njoku *et al.*, (2016) Thirty-one sampling locations are assessed for carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), oxygen (O₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), nitrogen oxide (NO), suspended particulate matter (SPM), and noise level using air pollutants measurement methods approved by ASTM for each specific parameter. All equipment and meters are properly pre-calibrated before each usage for quality assurance. Findings of the study showed that measured levels of noise (61.4 - 101.4 dBA), NO (0.0 - 3.0 ppm), NO₂ (0.0 - 3.0 ppm), CO (1.0 – 42.0 ppm), and SPM (0.14 – 4.82 ppm) in all sampling areas are quite high. Above regulatory limits, however, there was no significant difference except in SPM (at all the sampling points) and noise, NO₂, and NO (only in major traffic intersections). The air quality index (AQI) indicates that the ambient air can be described as poor for SPM, varying from good to very poor for CO, while NO and NO₂ are very good except at major traffic intersections where they are both poor and very poor (D-E). The results suggest that strict and appropriate vehicle emission management, industrial air pollution control, and close burning management of wastes should be considered in the study area to reduce the risks associated with these pollutants.

Khairul (2011) In the Modern era, environmental issues have significantly impacted human life. Air pollution indoor and outdoor environments are sometimes dangerous to human health, and it needs to be justified. The tile measurement process and technique should be used to fulfil this purpose. Therefore, several air quality parameters sensors are developed in the mobile robot in this research. The robot is controlled using a remote control and a wireless connection system. The air quality in the target area will be monitored by using sensors that will capture data and

send it to the Central Control (laptop) for analysis. And then, to be able to monitor certain area investigations, the mobile robot is guided by using a wireless camera. The result from this project can make the user monitor and navigate the target area using a mobile robot, which can make the user know the situation in that area. PIC16F887A has been chosen in this project as the main device controlling all activities of the mobile robot. Data capture and robot movement have been done in wireless to make it the user easy to do the monitoring activities. From the result, knowing that the error percentage of the data capture is small compared to the digital meter. So that knowing this project is effective because it makes it easy to do the air pollution monitoring process and can prevent gas poisoning cases from happening.

Reggente *et al.*, (2018) The EU project DustBot addresses urban hygiene. Two types of robots are designed, the DustClean Robot to autonomously clean pedestrian areas and the DustCart Robot for door-to-door garbage collection. Three prototype robots are built and equipped with electronic noses to enable them to collect environmental data while performing their urban hygiene tasks. Essentially, the robots act as mobile, wireless nodes in a sensor network. This research gives an overview of the DustBot platform focusing on the Air Monitoring Module (AMM). I describe the data flow between the robots through the ubiquitous network to a gas distribution modelling server, where a gas distribution model is computed. I describe the Kernel DM+V algorithm, an approach to creating statistical gas distribution models in the form of predictive mean and variance discretized onto a grid map. Finally, I present and discuss results obtained with the DustBot AMM during experimental trials performed in outdoor public places: a courtyard in Pontedera, Italy, and a pedestrian square in Orebro, Siden. In this research, i have briefly described the DustBot system, where an autonomous network of cooperating robots, while dealing with urban hygiene, also performs pollution monitoring in their work area (mostly

pedestrian areas). Then i have shown results from pollution monitoring trials carried out in two public spaces in Italy and Siden. The results show that the gas distribution model used (Kernel DM+V) is useful for high-resolution pollution monitoring. It can localize the gas source location using the information obtained by the variance map.

Asad *et al.*, (2017) Robots are being developed and utilized as a fundamental data collection tool for environmental monitoring to meet the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA). Monitoring factors such as temperature, humidity, CO levels, etc., is a major concern to businesses, educational institutions, and health organizations because it can significantly impact individuals' health, comfort, ill-being, and productivity. Sensor data collected can provide the necessary Indoor Air Quality information to the designers and the maintenance crew to take the corrective measures to meet the standards of the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE). Furthermore, the environmental monitoring robot with automated machines and sensors can take the place of humans to collect data in dangerous environments. To address the issues of environmental factors and to meet the requirement of the Senior/Capstone design project course, students worked in a team to design, develop and test a mobile Robotic System to monitor and map data from the environmental sensors in a well-defined trajectory in an academic building. The Environmental Monitoring Robotic System consists of an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) supported by the encoders on the Robot base to determine the robot's location and a Kinect@ Microsoft Inc. camera to detect objects and obstacles in the trajectory. The proposed systems also consist of the Robot Operating System (ROS) and sensor section for monitoring the environment. The ROS section is used for mapping and localization of the mobile robot. The navigation stack in ROS is used for the autonomous operation of the robot to move through a predetermined path to map data from the environmental

sensors. The sensor section includes the humidity sensor, temperature sensor, and a sensor for detecting the presence of different gases like CO, methane, propane, and LPG. This research discusses the design, development, programming, and implementation of a robotic platform to monitor environmental changes. This research also introduces an approach which enables students to work in teams to develop hardware/software systems.

Obanya *et al.*, (2018) Air quality was poor, especially PM concentrations in the study area around TSLs. This pollutant was above the limits set by the USEPA and FMEnv at some sampling locations. Although the values of some other parameters are relatively high, they did not exceed set limits. Most assessed parameters are significantly higher than those measured around residential areas, except for CO. The high levels of air quality parameters detected in some of the sampling locations in the present study are a greater consideration than the extent to which they exceeded set limits, as chronic exposure to minute concentrations plays a greater role in toxicology than acute exposures. The effects of poor air quality on public health and urban wildlife are a cause for concern given the increasing incidence of cancer diagnosis in Nigeria and the existing pressure on wildlife. In keeping with the current trend globally, developing countries such as Nigeria must embrace cleaner technology and continually reduce the levels of fossil fuels used in automobiles and internal combustion systems by adopting more efficient technologies. The legislature should enforce this with feasible timelines considering public health and economic factors.

Nwokocha *et al.*, (2018) A 13-days mean concentration of Sulphur dioxide (So₂), Nitrogen dioxide (No₂), Hydrogen sulfide (H₂s), Particulate matter (PM₁₀), Ammonia NH₃, Methane CH₄, and Carbon Monoxide (CO) are measured in some areas of Port Harcourt. The measurements are made to characterize air pollution in the urban environment of Port Harcourt

to assist in the development of an air quality index. The data are analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean). They are used to create multi-bar charts. A t-test was performed to compare means for seasons, and Pearson's correlation was used to determine a correlation between pollutants and meteorological data. Statistics are performed using the comprehensive statistical software (SPSS Version 17). The analysis shows a significantly strong positive correlation between SO₂ concentration and all other parameters and a significantly negative correlation between NO₂ concentration and other parameters.

The emission of these gases, Sulphur dioxide SO₂, Nitrogen dioxide NO₂, Ammonia NH₄, Carbon Monoxide CO, Hydrogen Sulphide H₂S and Particulate matter as greenhouse gases have contributed greatly to environmental problems in the Niger Delta as the hub of oil production in Nigeria as indicated in this study. Several studies have shown the links between greenhouse gases, air pollution, ozone layer depletion, and chronic health challenges. As recorded by (Samet, Dominici, and Curriero, 2021.) stating that greenhouse gases are major contributors to air pollution, for which its level has been linked strongly to mortality and morbidity from cardiopulmonary and cerebrovascular diseases, lung cancer, and infant mortality in the United States of America.

Prabha *et al.*, (2014) Cloud robotics is an emerging field centered on the benefits of a cloud computing environment, which is converged infrastructure and shared services. In this research, a system is designed with an autonomous robot to sense environmental data such as temperature, humidity, and air quality, along with GPS coordinates, and store them in the cloud. The mobile robot is controlled using an Arduino microcontroller and communicates with the cloud via a Raspberry Pi. A private cloud is set up using OpenStack, which provides infrastructure as a Service. The collected data are stored in a cloud server which can be viewed through a web

browser and can be used to create awareness about the environmental changes of the location under study. A proof-of-concept prototype has been developed to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed system. In this research, i have proposed a design of a smart cloud robot to monitor the environmental condition of a remote place. A prototype has been developed and tested on our campus to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. The system submits the collected data to the cloud and displays it on the web for further investigation. Storage is one of the challenges of the mobile robot, which is being addressed in this contribution.

Hasan *et al.*, (2019) Environmental monitoring systems are often designed to measure and log an environment's current status or establish trends in environmental parameters. This research proposed an autonomous robotic system to monitor environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, air quality, and harmful gas concentration. The robot has GPS coordinates, and it can store data on the ThingSpeak IoT platform. The mobile robot is controlled by a smartphone that runs an app built on the Android platform. The whole system is realized using a cost-effective ARM-based embedded system called Arduino and Raspberry Pi, which communicates through a wireless network to the IoT platform. Data are stored, processed, and accessed using a computer or other smart device. The system can update sensor data to the IoT server every 15 seconds. The stored data can be used to further analyses the reduction of pollution, save energy, and provide an overall living environment enhancement.

The robotic system has been designed for cost-effective remote monitoring of environmental parameters without human intervention to avoid health risks efficiently. A proof-of-concept prototype has been developed to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed system. In this present work, the design and implementation of a GPS-controlled robot for environmental parameters monitoring based on IoT and ARM have been accomplished. The developed ARM-

based embedded system with the IoT platform can monitor environmental parameters, and air quality measurement is compact and cost-effective. The results obtained are found to be useful for monitoring real-time environmental conditions. The developed App allows the user to control and navigate the robot easily. The GPS-controlled feature allows it to travel autonomously to remote places, submit the collected data to the IoT server, and display it on the web for high-level data analysis and processing. Graphical visualization evidence shows that the robotic system works efficiently.

Moreover, the system's key advantages are the intuitive user interfaces in the App and Autonomous movement after getting instruction from the user. Also, the system is cost-effective, and the costs are less than 80 USD. It updates sensor data to the IoT server every 15 seconds. Secured data in IoT platforms can be accessed from anywhere. Future work includes several features, including solar power and advanced communication solutions for rural areas. The system can be modified to detect radiation and other harmful gas autonomously to avoid human health risks. Also, the design method can be applied to drone technology to make it even more dynamic.

Trincavelli *et al.*, (2008) This research presents initial experiments toward environmental monitoring with a mobile platform. A prototype of a pollution monitoring robot was set up, which measures the gas distribution using an "electronic nose" and provides three-dimensional wind measurements using an ultrasonic anemometer. I describe the design of the robot and the experimental setup used to run trials under varying environmental conditions. I then present the results of the gas distribution mapping. The trials carried out in three uncontrolled environments with very different properties: an enclosed indoor area, a part of a long corridor with open ends and a high ceiling, and an outdoor scenario are presented and discussed.

2.2 Data Capture and Data Mining of Urban Air Pollution

In the Building-Based Approach, the method and accuracy of data capture dominate the spatial distribution of urban air pollution. Due to limited budget, installation space, and labor resources, permanent or temporary air pollution monitoring sites are scattered. A city's air quality assessment based on scattered monitoring sites may be incorrect because the nonhomogeneous distribution of air quality is neglected. Therefore, several model systems have been developed to estimate urban air quality at unsampled sites. The results show that the building-based approach may open an innovative methodology in data mining of urban spatial data for environmental assessment.

2.3 Design and implementation of a Multi-Functional Mobile Robot

An intelligent multi-functional mobile robot is presented in this research. The hardware involves the ultrasonic sensor, Bluetooth device, wireless camera, DC servo motor, and mechanical gripper. One single ultrasound sensor is programmed to seek the object to complete the object localization. A human-machine interface is developed to control the mobile robot remotely. Exploring a tiny and harsh environment can be carried out using wireless communication and a camera. Hardware description language is used in the controller design and the peripheral I/O circuit. The human-machine interface is completed in C language (Ying, 2002).

2.4 Air Pollution

Air pollution introduces chemicals, particulate matter, or biological materials that cause harm or discomfort to humans or other living organisms or damage the natural environment into the atmosphere. The atmosphere is a complex dynamic natural gaseous system essential to support

life on planet Earth. Stratospheric ozone depletion due to air pollution has long been recognized as a threat to human health and ecosystems. Indoor air pollution and urban air quality are listed as two of the world's worst pollution problems (Turner, 2016).

2.5 Health Effects of Air Pollution

This research provides background reading for the Population-Environment Research network's online seminar. This seminar aims to foster a discussion that will lead to identifying key issues, knowledge gaps, and methodological shortcomings in understanding the health impacts of air pollution, both indoors and outdoors (Vinod, 2003).

2.6 Environment Sensing

The robotic system uses sensors such as the DHT11 Temperature and Humidity Sensor, MQ-7 Carbon-monoxide Gas Sensor and MQ135 Air Quality Sensor. The system also can monitor environmental parameters such as CO₂ and smoke. The DHT11 is a digital temperature and humidity sensor. It uses a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor to measure the surrounding air and spits out a digital signal on the data pin. The air quality sensor is the MQ-135 sensor for detecting toxic gases present in the air. Being a very dangerous gas, Carbon monoxide (CO) is odorless and colorless, so it cannot be smelt, seen, or tasted, which makes it difficult to detect. MQ7 Carbon Monoxide (CO) gas sensor detects the concentrations of CO in the air and outputs its reading as an analogue voltage anywhere from 20 to 2021ppm. This sensor has high sensitivity and a fast response time. There is a screw potentiometer that enables manual adjustments to the output gain of the sensor. The ADS1015 converts analogue data to digital data received from both sensors.

2.7 Navigation and Control Hardware for Navigation

The system requires the GPS module Ubox NEO-6M and the compass HMC5883L with Arduino mega. A global Positioning System (GPS) is a satellite-based navigation system that provides critical positioning capabilities to the robot. Along the way, The HC-SR04 ultrasonic distance sensor is used for obstacle detection. L293D motor shield controls the robot's movement according to its Navigation. The HMC5883L is a triple-axis magnetometer that uses the basic principle behind electromagnets to sense the magnetic north pole. This compact sensor uses I2C to communicate. The L293D, a motor driver, is an integrated circuit chip usually used to control motors in robots.

2.8 The Pollution Monitoring Robot

Apart from a laser range scanner (SICK LMS 200) used for localization, the robot used in the experiments is equipped with an "electronic nose" and an anemometer. The "electronic nose" comprises six gas sensors enclosed in an aluminum tube. This tube is horizontally mounted on the front side of the robot at the height of 34 cm (Figure 2.2). The "electronic nose" is actively ventilated through a fan that creates a constant airflow towards the gas sensors. Thus, it lowers the effect of external airflow and the robot's movement on the sensor response and guarantees a continuous gas exchange in situations with very low external airflow. Different sensors are chosen so that the "electronic nose" can respond to various gases. In this work, however, i consider the case of a single gas source only. The ultrasonic anemometer used to measure the airflow is a Young 81000 with a range from 2 cm/s up to 40 m/s with a resolution of 1 cm/s. I know from experience in indoor gas-distribution measurements that the airflow field and the resultant gas distribution can be three dimensional in some environments. The placement of the

anemometer had to be a compromise between the desire to measure the airflow as close to the gas sensors and as undisturbed as possible. It was finally placed above the top of the robot to minimize the influence of the fan of the "electronic nose", the advective flow created by the heated metal oxide sensors, and the robot's body.

Figure 2.1: The pollution monitoring robot “Rasmus” is equipped with an "electronic nose"

("e-nose") and an anemometer (Bray, 2020).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 The following materials are used

This research work, which developed a low-cost air quality monitor to detect PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, Oxides of Nitrogen (NO_x) and Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC). The system was designed to operate as a rechargeable and portable unit, which measures air pollutants via low-cost sensor modules. Details of major materials used like names and their functions, are discussed in the table below. The system diagram is shown in Figure 3.1.

Serial Number	Name of Material	Function of Material in the device
1.	MQ-135 Sensor module	This sensor module is used to detect the presence of VOC and the corresponding value of concentration in the atmosphere.
2.	MQ-3 Sensor module	This sensor module is used to detect the presence of NO _x gases and the value of concentration in the atmosphere.
3.	Arduino Atmega328p	It is used to process the

		measured signals from the sensor modules and determine the concentration of the gases and particulate matter status in real-time. It also aids interaction between the other components.
4.	PMS5003 Sensor Module	This sensor module is used to detect the presence of Particulate Matter 1, 2.5 and 10 and their value of concentration in the atmosphere.
5.	Breadboard	Breadboards allow easy replacement of components.
6.	Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) Screen	This is used to project the values from the sensors in a form of feedback.
7.	EEPROM (electrically erasable programmable read-only memory)	Installed for the purpose of storing small amounts of data in computing and other electronic devices.

Table3.1: Details of major materials used, their names and their functions.

Asides from the Arduino microcontroller, sensor modules in the device and the LCD screen mentioned earlier, other components include jumper wire, used to connect the sensor modules to the board, a USB cable which serves as power source when connected to a laptop or a power-bank, ESP-01 adapter which is used for programming, and for the purpose of storing small amounts of data in computing and other electronic devices, an EEPROM (electrically erasable programmable read-only memory) was installed in the device, followed by a 10k potentiometer for the purpose of controlling the flow of electricity through the device circuit.

The whole components are joined together by soldering on a breadboard and placed in an enclosed plastic container after which it was sealed.

Figure 3.1: The block diagram of the system design

3.2 Process of development

The major chip of the system is gas sensing analyzer. Using jumper wares, the sensor modules chosen (the MQ-135 gas sensor module, the MQ-3 and the PMS5003 sensor module for Particulate Matter), are interfaced with a microcontroller development board (Arduino ATmega), which is a modern microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P, to process the measured signals and determine the concentration of the gas and particulate matter in real-time. The analogue pin is then related to the analogue pin 0 and the digital pin to digital 8 on the Arduino board, while +5V and the GND (ground) pins on the sensors' unit are linked to the 5V Voltage common collector (Vcc) and GND (ground) pin correspondingly on the Arduino board. The LCD screen was connected to the Arduino Uno board by relating the serial data pin (SDA) pin on the display to the A4 pin on the Arduino board, the clock line (SCL) on the display to A5 on the Arduino board. Finally, connect Vcc to 5V on the Arduino board and the gnd to ground.

The Arduino Uno board is then interfaced with a personal computer for programming and data acquisition through a USB connection computer system via a USB cable. The Arduino board is programmed using Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) software, with built-in example code known as sketches. It was powered by a built-in battery and alternatively by a power bank or laptop USB port after it has been programmed. The components are then placed in an enclosed developed plastic container after which it was sealed. These are the device's hardware and software components and development process. The values are printed on a low-power LCD screen, which provides the user with constant feedback.

Figure 3.2: Complete Circuit Diagram

PLATE 3.1: The Soldering aspect of the development process.

Plate3.2: Showing the Arduino Uno, and the LCD screen, and the breadboard.

3.3 Field of study

To assess the performance of the developed monitor, the developed device and the purchased Industrial-Made device are deployed to Dugbe Motor Park, with a high traffic density with latitude and longitude of 7.78247⁰N and 4.54870⁰, Oke-fia busy road intersection, with latitude and longitude of 7.78414⁰N and 4.54550⁰E and lastly Igbona Market on its market day with latitude and longitude of 7.78096⁰N and 4.55743⁰E, which are all located in *Osogbo*, Osun State, South-west Nigeria. All the three locations have high density of human and vehicular traffic.

Measurements of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and VOC are carried out for six (6) days, spending two (2) consecutive days at a location before moving to another location with both devices. Measurements for NO_x are taken but not compared because the purchased industrial-made device does not possess the feature for sensing the concentration. The data are taken simultaneously for twelve (12) hours with a ten (10) minute range. Seventy-two (72) readings are obtained from each device making a total of one hundred and forty-four (144) readings. To minimize the risk of contamination or error in measurement, both devices are placed on a brick of size 315mm x 165mm x 148mm. The measurement was carried out on days when there was no rainfall.

3.4 Particulate Matter

A large number of sources contribute to ambient airborne PM. These include: motor vehicles; power plants; smelters; quarries and cement industries; suspended and windblown dust; photochemical processes producing secondary PM, and tobacco smoke. Airborne particles can be classified and characterized in a number of ways, for example; according to their physical, chemical or biological properties.

Particle size is of particular importance, as health and environmental exposures to and effects of particles depend strongly on this parameter. Particle size is a consequence of the process that resulted in its generation, and thus is also dependent on the source and its characteristics.

Various classifications and terminologies have been used to define particle size ranges. The division most commonly used is between fine and coarse particles, with the boundary between these two fractions widely accepted as 2.5 μm . The terminology that has been used in the nomenclature of the ambient air quality standards, and also for characterization of indoor and outdoor particle mass concentrations, includes PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ fractions and the total suspended particulate matter (TSP). PM_{2.5} (fine particles) and PM₁₀ are the mass concentrations of particles with aerodynamic diameters smaller than 2.5 μm and 10 μm , respectively.

PM_{2.5} particles mainly generated by combustion, gas to particle conversion, nucleation processes or photochemical processes. Due to their size, PM_{2.5} particles can penetrate further down in the respiratory system compared to larger particles.

PM₁₀ is denoted as the coarse particle fraction. PM₁₀ particles result mainly from mechanical processes such as cutting, grinding, breaking and wear of material and dust resuspension. TSP is the mass concentration of all particles suspended in the air. Although coarse particle size ranges may cause significant local nuisance or soiling impacts, it is the finer fractions, such as PM_{2.5} or PM₁ (particles of size smaller than 1 μm) that are capable of deep airway/lung penetration. (Akira *et al.*, 2018)

3.5 Volatile Organic Compounds

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are of concern as both indoor and outdoor air pollutants. Common VOCs include trichloroethylene, benzene, toluene, and alcohols. VOCs are mostly reported as total VOC (TVOC) readings. This term recognizes the combined effect of compounds that may not

otherwise have been captured, due to low concentration levels. A low TVOC value usually indicates that there is no VOC problem; however, a high TVOC value may result from a high level of a single compound or from a vast collection of low compound levels. Sources indicate that TVOC concentrations between 50 and 325 ppb are acceptable and should not exceed 500 ppb.

3.6 The air quality index (AQI)

It is an index for reporting daily air quality. It is used to communicate to the public on how clean or unhealthy the ambient air is with all the associated health effects which might be of concern. The higher the AQI value, the greater the level of air pollution and the greater the health concern. The AQI is divided into six categories, table 3.2 summarizes the AQI, descriptor and color codes.

Air Quality Index (AQI) Values	Descriptor	Colors code
0–50	Good	Green
51–100	Moderate	Yellow
101–150	Unhealthy sensitive groups	Orange
151–200	Unhealthy	Red
201–300	Very unhealthy	Purple
301 and higher	Hazardous	Maroon

Table 3.2 summarizes the AQI, descriptor and color codes. (Fakinle *et.al.*, 2013)

Breaking points PM _{2.5} (µg m ⁻³)	Breaking points PM ₁₀ (µg m ⁻³)	AQI	AQI Ratings
0.0–12.0	0–54	0–50	A
12.1–35.4	55–154	51–100	B
35.5–55.4	155–254	101–150	C
55.5–150.4	255–354	151–200	D
150.5–250.4	355–424	201–300	E
250.5–350.4	425–504	301–400	F
350.5–500	505–604	401–500	G

Table 3.3: Air quality index for pollutant. (Fakinle *et.al.*, 2013)

3.7 Toxicity Potential

Fakinle *et.al.*, (2013) reported that the studies on toxicity potential of Particulate Matter have predicated upon growing human health concern about PM inhalation. Particulate matter of various toxicities has been known to pose severe health hazards due to the theoretical evaluation of the extremely negative effects of particulate matter through metal-generated free radicals and that the calculated toxicity potential value that exceeds unity using the threshold limits is worrisome.

S/N	Components	Quantity	Cost (₦)
1.	MQ-135 Sensor module	1	5,400
2.	MQ-3 Sensor module	1	4,500
3.	Arduino Atmega328p	1	13,050
4.	PMS5003 Sensor Module	1	11,700
5.	Breadboard	1	7,650
6.	LCD Screen	1	4950
7.	EEPROM (electrically erasable programmable read-only memory)	1	4,500
8.	ESP-01 adapter	1	6,300
9.	10k potentiometer	4	4500
10.	jumper ware	1	1000
11.	Plastic Casing	1	3,750
12.	Resistors (1k Ω ,)	4	2,300
	TOTAL		69,600

Table 3.4: List of Materials for Developed device

Plate3.3: Major components being coupled.

3.8 Air Quality Standards

An air quality standard defines the maximum amount of a pollutant averaged over a specified period of time that can be present in outdoor air without harming public health, and thus, it defines clean air. The Clean Air Act, which was last amended in 1990, requires EPA to set National Ambient Air Quality Standards (40 CFR part 50) for pollutants considered harmful to public health and the environment. The Clean Air Act identifies two types of national ambient air quality standards. Primary standards provide public health protection, including protecting the health of "sensitive" populations such as asthmatics, children, and the elderly. Secondary standards provide public welfare protection, including protection against decreased visibility and damage to animals, crops, vegetation, and buildings. (US EPA, 2022).

3.9 Air Quality Evaluation

Air quality prediction is mostly used as an important monitoring technique and evaluating the quality of air in the environment. The influence for supply of gas and its characteristics is its adaptability for specified purposes. Air pollutants are contaminations that can affect and endanger human health.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research is focused on Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) and Particulate Matter ($PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10}) which is one of the six principal pollutants, also known as criteria pollutants.

4.1 Particulate Matter (PM)

The concentration of the $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} for the developed device and the purchased Industrial-Made device are taken and compared to determine the device with the best performance and the device with cheaper cost. The values of concentration for the Particulate Matter are represented graphically for comparison of the performance of the two devices.

The two devices are placed around an untarred portion beside the busy road at Dugbe Motor Park, for day one. As shown in Figure 4.1 which is the concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ Measured in Day one for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices, the sensitivity of the developed device performed better than that of the purchased industrial-made device during the hours of 8:10am and 10:30am. At 10:40am there are movement of some heavy-duty trucks emitting smoke which caused a spike on the developed device. The spike for Purchased Industrial-Made device was as a result of dust being raised by speeding car convoy passing around that period. For this round of experimentation, the purchased Industrial-Made device has an increased value of concentration for the most part of the experimentation when compared with the developed device which is as a result of the nature of the environment (untarred portion of the road).

Figure 4.1: Concentration of PM_{2.5} Measured in Day one for both Developed and Purchased industrial-made devices.

Figure 4.2 which is the concentration of PM_{10} Measured in Day one for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices, showed that throughout the day, the purchased industrial-made device performed better than the developed device except some spikes that can be seen at 11:40am to 12:10am and between 6:10pm to 7:10pm which was as a result of a traffic congestion leading to dust being raised around where the devices are placed. Looking at the concentration of the Particulate Matter pollutants at the Dugbe Motor Park where this measurement was taken, it can be said that the Purchased Industrial-Made device performed better than the developed device.

Figure 4.2: Concentration of PM₁₀ Measured in Day 1 for both Developed and Purchased industrial-made devices.

On the second day, the study area was still the Dugbe Motor Park, and the devices maintained the same position as the previous day, besides the untarred portion of the only road around the motor park. Figure 4.3 indicates that the purchased industrial-made device showed better performance than the developed device, with the developed device showing random spikes due to trucks with billowing smoke from its exhaust passing by at different intervals when the Concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ was being measured.

Therefore, it can be noted that the purchased industrial-made device performed better where there is dust compared to the developed device.

Figure 4.3: Concentration of PM_{2.5} Measured on Day two for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

Figure 4.4 below illustrates the concentration of PM_{10} measured on day two. It can be seen that, from the beginning of the day and throughout the whole period of taking the concentration measurement, the purchased industrial-made device performed better. In contrast, the developed device experienced spikes at 12:10 pm and 1:30 pm, resulting from a petrol tanker passing on the road with smoke coming out of the exhaust.

Figure 4.4: Concentration of PM₁₀ Measured on Day two for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

On third day, the study area was the Igbona Market on a market day, associated with a high density of vehicular and human traffic. It has a tarred road running through it with a road divider where both the developed device and the Purchased Industrial-Made device are deployed for measurement. The tar on the road made it less dusty. From the results of the Concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ Measured on Day three for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices on the graph, it can be seen that the sensitivity of the developed device performed ill at the beginning of the day. A spike from around 8:50 am to about 9:00 am due to the movement of a dump truck on the road was noticed. After this, the sensitivity of the purchased Industrial-Made device picked up, and some spikes which happened due to the passing by of tankers was noticed. Overall, the sensitivity of the developed device gave a more accurate value of concentration for the measurement of $PM_{2.5}$ on the third day of experimentation when compared with that of the purchased Industrial-Made device. The result is graphically represented in Figure 4.5 below.

Figure 4.5: Concentration of PM_{2.5} Measured in Day three for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

Figure 4.6 is the concentration of PM_{10} measured in day three for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices. Just like for $PM_{2.5}$, the sensitivity of the developed device at the start of the experimentation the developed device performed better than the purchased industrial-made device with some spikes that can be seen at around 8:50 am to about 9:00 am which occurred as a result of the movement of some tankers around the vicinity of the devices. Same thing can be said for the spikes noticed throughout the duration of the experimentation for day four. For this round of the experimentation, it can be seen the differences between the concentration values are almost the same, looking at the graph, this is because the location has a relatively low dusty terrain where the devices are deployed. Hence the purchased industrial-made device couldn't give vast difference except for spikes as a result of occasional movement of heavy-duty vehicles passing. The developed device can be said to have performed better because the purchased industrial-made device is alien to this environment.

Figure 4.6: Concentration of PM₁₀ Measured in Day three for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

On the fourth day, the study area was at the Oke-fia Roundabout, the devices are placed close to a bad portion of the road where if there is vehicular movement, dust will be raised. Figure 4.7 is the graphical representation of the Concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ measured in Day four for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices, it can be seen that the purchased industrial-made device showed a better performance over the developed device, with the developed device showing random spikes as a result of trucks with billowing smokes passing by at different intervals when concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ was being Measured. At around 11:50am there was a prominent spike, which occurred when a bus swerved into the bad portion of the road where the devices are placed, raising a thick dust, covering both devices. Therefore, it can be noted that the purchased industrial-made device performed better where there is dust compared to the developed device.

Figure 4.7: Concentration of PM_{2.5} Measured in Day four for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

Figure 4.8 below illustrates the concentration of PM_{10} measured on day four. From the beginning of the day and throughout the whole period of taking the concentration measurement, the purchased industrial-made device performed better though there are prominent spikes around 11:50am and 2:40pm, this occurred when a bus swerved into the bad portion of the road where the devices are placed, raising a thick dust, covering both devices. while the developed device experienced spikes at 8:30am, 11:50am, 3:40pm and 7:50pm, which is as a result of a petrol tanker passing on the road with smoke coming out of its exhaust, a speeding police escort convoy, and a cement truck moving on the road.

Figure 4.8: Concentration of PM₁₀ Measured in Day four for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

On the fifth day, the devices are deployed back to Igbona Market, to make up for twenty-four hours of concentration values measurement. Just as on day three of the experimentation, the devices are placed on a nine inches block kept on the road divider. From the graphical representation of the data gotten from the experimentation Figure 4.9 below, the developed device showed it performed ill at the beginning of the day and a spike was noticed at around 8:30am which was as a result of the movement of a trailer carrying cement on the road. After this, the sensitivity of the purchased industrial-Made device picked up and some little spikes are noticed which happened due to the passing by of tankers at about 2:10pm. Overall, the sensitivity of the developed device gave a more accurate value of concentration for the measurement of $PM_{2.5}$ on the fifth day of experimentation when compared with that of the purchased industrial-made device.

Figure 4.9: Concentration of PM_{2.5} Measured in Day five for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

Figure 4.10 is the graphical representation of the concentration of PM_{10} Measured in Day five for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices at Igbona Market, just like for the $PM_{2.5}$, the sensitivity of the developed device at the start of the experimentation the developed device performed better than the purchased industrial-made device with some spikes that can be seen at around 8:30am which was as a result of the movement of a trailer carrying cement on the road. The purchased industrial-made device also showed some great performance as can be seen at around 12:20pm to 4:00pm which was when the market was full and there was congestion of traffic, extending to where the devices are place, making a dumpster to be delayed at the point, resulting in the air around there to be polluted for long. At the end of the experimentation, it can be deduced that the developed device did perform better than the purchased industrial-made device.

Figure 4.10: Concentration of PM₁₀ Measured in Day five for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

On the sixth day which was the final day of experimentation, the devices are deployed back to Oke-fia round about. The values of concentration measured for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are graphically represented in Figure 4.11 and Figure 4.12 below respectively. Figure 4.11 which is the value of concentration for PM_{2.5} for day six, it can be seen that the purchased industrial-made device showed a better performance over the developed device, with the developed device showing random spikes at 11:30am and at 3:40pm as a result of trucks with billowing smokes passing by at different intervals purchased industrial-made device spikes can be seen at 12:30pm, 3:40pm and 8:00pm which are noticed when there was dust raised due to the movement of heavy duty trucks.

Figure 4.11: Concentration of PM_{2.5} Measured in Day six for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

Figure 4.12 below, illustrates the concentration of PM_{10} measured in day six it can be seen that, from the beginning of the day and throughout the whole period of taking the concentration measurement, the purchased industrial-made device performed better though there are prominent spikes around 12:30pm, 3:40pm and 8:00pm, this occurred when a bus swerved into the bad portion of the road where the devices are placed, raising a thick dust, covering both devices. while the developed device experienced spikes at 11:30am, 12:30pm and 3:40pm, which occurred mainly as a result of a delivery truck passing on the road with smoke coming out of the exhaust, a police escort convoy, and a tipper truck moving on the road.

Figure 4.12: Concentration of PM₁₀ Measured in Day six for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

4.2 Air quality index (AQI) Calculation

The AQI around the three (3) locations was calculated using the EPA (2006) method in Equation (4.1).

$$I_p = \frac{I_{Hi} - I_{Lo}}{BP_{Hi} - BP_{Lo}} (C_p - BP_{Lo}) + I_{Lo}$$

(4.1)

Where:

I_p = The index for pollutant p, C_p = The rounded concentration of pollutant p, BP_{Hi} = The breakpoint that is greater than or equal to C_p as given in Table 3.3, BP_{Lo} = The breakpoint that is less than or equal to C_p as given in Table 3.3, I_{Hi} = The AQI value corresponding to BP_{Hi} , I_{Lo} = The AQI value corresponding to BP_{Lo} .

The results are in Tables 4.1 to 4.4 below.

LOCATION	DAY 1(μgm^{-3})	DAY 2(μgm^{-3})	AVERAGE(μgm^{-3})
Dugbe Motor Park	30.81	19.79	25.3
Oke-fia	23.99	8.15	16.07
Igbona Market	11.10	28.05	19.58

Table 4.1: Extrapolated 24hr averaging period (PM2.5) from the measured levels

(Developed device).

LOCATION	DAY 1(μgm^{-3})	DAY 2(μgm^{-3})	AVERAGE(μgm^{-3})
Dugbe Motor Park	31.65	21.84	26.75
Oke-fia	34.08	12.38	23.23
Igbona Market	15.09	34.28	24.69

Table 4.2: Extrapolated 24hr averaging period (PM2.5) from the measured levels

(Purchased industrial-made device).

LOCATION	DAY 1(μgm^{-3})	DAY 2(μgm^{-3})	AVERAGE(μgm^{-3})
Dugbe Motor Park	36.15	22.72	29.44
Oke-fia	27.82	48.93	38.38
Igbona Market	13.06	48.82	30.94

Table 4.3: Extrapolated 24hr averaging period (PM10) from the measured levels

(Developed device).

LOCATION	DAY 1(μgm^{-3})	DAY 2(μgm^{-3})	AVERAGE(μgm^{-3})
Dugbe Motor Park	58.63	40.05	49.34
Oke-fia	62.17	67.06	64.62
Igbona Market	82.82	58.62	70.72

**Table 4.4: Extrapolated 24hr averaging period (PM10) from the measured levels
(Purchased industrial-made device).**

LOCATION	AQI(PM _{2.5})	AQI Ratings (PM _{2.5})	AQI (PM ₁₀)	AQI Ratings (PM ₁₀)
Dugbe Motor Park	25.13	A	29.44	A
Oke-Fia	16.07	A	38.38	A
Igbona	19.58	A	30.94	A

Table 4.5: AQI rating for the study areas (Developed device).

LOCATION	AQI(PM _{2.5})	AQI Ratings (PM _{2.5})	AQI(PM ₁₀)	AQI Ratings (PM ₁₀)
Dugbe Motor Park	26.75	A	49.34	A
Oke-fia	23.23	A	64.62	B
Igbona	24.69	A	70.72	B

Table 4.6: AQI rating for the study areas (Purchased industrial-made device)

4.3 Toxicity Potential

The 24-hr averaging period extrapolated concentrations of the measured Toxicity Potential are computed using an atmospheric stability formula (Fakinle et.al., 2013) given in Equation (4.2) as

$$C_0 = C_1 \times F \quad (4.2)$$

Where:

C_0 = the concentration at the averaging period t_0

C_1 = the concentration at the averaging period t_1

F = factor to convert from the averaging period t_1 to the averaging period $t_0 = \left(\frac{t_1}{t_0}\right)^n$

$n = 0.28$, the stability dependent exponent.

Toxicity potential expressed as the ratio of measured ambient PM concentration to the statutory limit of ambient concentration (Fakinle *et.al.*, 2013) is useful in assessing the deleterious effects of the high density of vehicular emissions on human health. It was computed using Equation (4.3) taking into consideration the ambient air quality standards of TSP by the Federal Ministry of Environment (FMENV) whose value is $250 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, World Bank (WB) which is $80 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, and the World Health Organization (WHO) which is ($150 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) lower and upper ($230 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) as reported in FEPA (1991) World Bank (1998) and WHO (1979) respectively.

$$\text{Toxicity Potential} = \frac{M_{\text{TSP}}}{S_{\text{TSP}}} \quad (4.3)$$

Where;

M_{TSP} is the measured Total Suspended Particulate and

S_{TSP} is the statutory limit set for Total Suspended Particulates (TSP)

4.4 Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC)

For this research, the concentration of the Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) for the developed device and the purchased Industrial-Made device are taken and compared to determine the device with the best performance and the device with cheaper cost. The values of concentration measured are represented graphically for comparison of the performance of the two devices.

To measure the Value of concentration for Day one, the devices are deployed to Dugbe Motor Park in Osogbo and readings are taken for 12 hours, with 10 minutes interval. The results are graphically represented in Figure 4.13 below.

Figure 4.13, shows the results for both developed device and purchased industrial-Made device, where it can be deduced that between the period of 8:10am-3:10pm there was no significant change in the Values of concentration of the Volatile Organic Compounds in the developed device, whereas the purchased industrial-made device had significant high values and intermittent spikes as a result of movement of vehicles. At around 3:40pm there was a little rise in Value of concentration on the developed device, which was noticed during the passing of a flatbed trailer with a Caterpillar on it. At about 5:40pm to 6:40pm the purchased industrial-made device experienced a spike which was when a traffic congestion happened. The high values on the Purchased Industrial-Made device can be attributed to the fact that the Purchased Industrial-Made device is alien to this environment, because it was sourced from abroad with a different environment and level of pollution.

Figure 4.13: Concentration of VOC Measured in Day one for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

To measure the Value of concentration for Day two, the devices are deployed to Dugbe Motor Park in Osogbo and readings are taken for 12 hours, with 10 minutes interval. The results are graphically represented in Figure 4.14, which is for both developed device and purchased industrial-Made device, where it can be deduced that all through the day there was no significant change in the Values of concentration of the Volatile Organic Compounds in the developed device, whereas the purchased industrial-made device had significant high values and intermittent spikes as a result of movement of vehicles. At around 9:30am a sudden spike was noticed in the Value of concentration on the developed device, which was noticed during the passing of a petrol tanker. After then, the purchased industrial-made device experienced intermittent spike which was when a traffic congestion happened. The high values on the purchased industrial-made device can be attributed to the fact that the device is alien to this environment, because it was sourced from abroad with a different environment and standard level of pollution.

Figure 4.14: Concentration of VOC Measured in Day two for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

To measure the Value of concentration for Day three, the devices are deployed to Igbona Market in Osogbo on a market day and readings are taken for 12 hours, with 10 minutes interval. The results are graphically represented in Figure 4.15, which is for both developed device and purchased industrial-Made device, where it can be deduced that all through the day there was a noticeable rise in the Values of concentration of the Volatile Organic Compounds in the developed device at about 11:30am extending to the rest of the day, which was as a result of the market being crowded and spilling onto the road, causing slow movement of vehicular traffic. Whereas the purchased industrial-made device had significant high values and intermittent spikes due to the same reason as above. At around 10:40am, 11:20am, 11:50am, 5:50pm and 7:10pm a sudden spike noticed in the value of concentration on the developed device, which was noticed during the passing of petrol tankers. The high values on the purchased industrial-made device can be attributed to the fact that the device is alien to this environment, because it was sourced from abroad with a different environment and standard level of pollution.

Figure 4.15: Concentration of VOC Measured in Day three for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

To measure the Value of concentration for Day four, the devices are deployed to Igbona Market in Osogbo on a market day. The results are graphically represented in Figure 4.16, which is for both developed device and purchased industrial-Made device, where it can be seen that all through the day there was no noticeable rise in the values of concentration of the Volatile Organic Compounds in the developed device all through the period of experimentation. Whereas the purchased industrial-made device had significant high values and intermittent spikes due to traffic congestions around the roundabout as a result of cars waiting for signals from the traffic wardens. At around 8:30am, 11:50am a sudden spike was noticed in the Value of concentration on the purchased industrial-made device, which was noticed during the passing of petrol tankers. The high values on the purchased industrial-made device can be attributed to the fact that the device is alien to this environment, because it was sourced from abroad with a different environment and standard level of pollution.

Figure 4.16: Concentration of VOC Measured in Day four for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

To measure the Value of concentration for Day 5, the devices are deployed to Igbona Market in Osogbo on a market day. The results representing the Value of concentration of Volatile Organic Compounds measured in day five are graphically represented in the Figure 4.17 below and it can be seen that from the beginning of the day and throughout the whole period of taking the concentration measurement, it was noticed the purchased industrial-made device values has spikes at different periods which was as a result of a petrol tankers passing on and it can be inferred that all through the day there was a noticeable rise in the Values of concentration of the Volatile Organic Compounds in the developed device at about 10:20am extending to the rest of the day, which was as a result of the market being crowded and spilling onto the road, causing slow movement of vehicular traffic.

Figure 4.17: Concentration of VOC Measured in Day five for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

To measure the Value of concentration of Volatile Organic Compounds for Day six, the devices are deployed to Oke-fia roundabout in Osogbo and readings are taken for 12 hours, with 10 minutes interval. The results representing the value of concentration of Volatile Organic Compounds measured in day 6 are graphically represented in the Figure 4.17 below and it can be seen that from the beginning of the day and throughout the whole period of taking the concentration measurement, it was noticed the purchased industrial-made device values has spikes at around 2:20pm, 3:40pm, and 8:00pm which was as a result of a petrol tankers passing on and it can be inferred that all through the day there was a noticeable rise in the values of concentration of the Volatile Organic Compounds in the developed device at about 9:20am to 9:50, 5:40, 6:40pm and 7:50pm, which was as a result of spikes due to traffic congestions around the roundabout as a result of cars waiting for signals from the traffic wardens. The high values on the purchased industrial-made device can be attributed to the fact that the device is alien to this environment, because it was sourced from abroad with a different environment and standard level of pollution.

Figure 4.18: Concentration of VOC Measured in Day six for both developed and purchased industrial-made devices.

4.5 Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was carried out with SPSS 25.0 and the descriptive statistics was compiled taking into consideration all of the devices together. Univariate method was applied to assess similarities, correlations or differences between datasets, all the data obtained are displayed in table 4.7. Mean differences between ambient pollutant concentration collected across all sampling sites are calculated using two sample t-tests with unequal variances. The concentrations of PM_{2.5} for industrial and developed ranged from 19.79±1.39 µg/m³ to 46.18±4.33 µg/m³ and 21.84±0.89 µg/m³ to 47.77±3.51 µg/m³ respectively, while the industrial and developed concentration of PM₁₀ ranged from 22.72±1.65 µg/m³ to 47.77±3.51 µg/m³ respectively. The concentration of VOC for industrial and developed devices ranged from 0.08±0.03 µg/m³ to 0.51±0.03 µg/m³ and 0.76±0.09 µg/m³ to 2.26±0.13 µg/m³. The summary of this data showed that the measured concentrations of these pollutants have a wide range of variability.

	PM_{2.5}		PM₁₀		VOC	
	DEVELOPE D	PURCHASE D	DEVELOPE D	PURCHASE D	DEVELOPE D	PURCHASE D
	8am-8pm	8am-8pm	8am-8pm	8am-8pm	8am-8pm	8am-8pm
Da y 1	30.81±2.40	31.65±1.41	36.15±3.02	58.63±1.19	0.13±0.01	1.33±0.09
Da y 2	19.79±1.39	21.84±0.89	22.72±1.65	40.05±1.62	0.08±0.03	0.76±0.09
Da y 3	46.18±4.33	47.77±3.51	55.67±5.86	82.82±5.09	0.43±0.03	2.26±0.13
Da y 4	23.99±2.09	34.08±2.37	27.82±2.60	62.17±3.92	0.11±0.01	1.55±0.10
Da y 5	28.05±3.69	34.28±1.81	34.10±4.98	58.62±2.97	0.51±0.03	1.75±0.11
Da y 6	26.42±2.22	37.05±2.47	30.96±2.79	67.06±3.62	0.17±0.02	1.61±0.10

Table 4.7: statistical summary

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

One of the main challenges in air quality management (AQM) is to have timely and appropriate access to air quality data which are relevant and of known quality. Air quality monitoring is one key element to allow effective decision-making on air quality issues. The monitoring of air quality provides the data required to assess compliance with current ambient air quality guidelines and standards and to assess trends in air pollutant concentrations. It can also be used to determine the effectiveness of existing and proposed policies.

In this research i developed an air quality monitoring device to check for concentrations of Particulate Matter, Volatile Organic Compounds and Oxides of Nitrogen. The concentrations of the Particulate Matter and the Volatile Organic Compounds of the developed device are compared with that of the Purchased Industrial-Made device to assess the performance of both devices and also the cost of purchase and development. Using the developed device, i can monitor air quality and evaluate the future prediction. I can get real time quality of air and evaluate it with aid of traditional air prediction techniques, big data technology, and machine learning techniques.

From this research, it is shown that the developed device has an advantage when it measures the Particulate Matter ($PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}) while the industrial made is advantageous when it is used to measure VOC based on the concentration when represented graphically.

5.2 Recommendation

Government funding is required for research into areas like air quality monitoring, which will improve the precision of data collection and lower health risks. This can be resolved by making funds accessible for academic research purpose.

Lack of awareness on the hazards associated with air pollution. The best method to solve this issue is to raise public awareness while simultaneously having scientists apply a multidisciplinary plan; national and international organisations must address the threat's escalation and offer long-term remedies.

In order to further reduce the health risks associated with holding handheld devices, future study should focus on web apps that facilitate accessibility to pollution data concentration. Government-led department should be established, that will be in charge of keeping data from research works like this and making it readily available for consumers.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: Table Showing the Concentrations for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x And VOC (24 Hours)

S/N	TIME	PM _{2.5} (µgm ⁻³)		PM ₁₀ (µgm ⁻³)		VOC(µgm ⁻³)		NO _x (µgm ⁻³)
		FAB	IND-MD	FAB	IND-MD	FAB	IND-MD	
1	8:10	68.88	50.84	84.46	87.74	0.08938	0.40426	71.34
2	8:20	78.72	46.74	97.58	87.74	0.11562	0.1312	83.64
3	8:30	62.32	43.46	75.44	80.36	0.0984	0.26896	72.16
4	8:40	54.12	41.82	63.96	77.9	0.11972	0.09758	84.46
5	8:50	45.92	40.18	54.12	77.9	0.0984	0.5453	72.98
6	9:00	53.3	40.18	62.32	75.44	0.11808	1.2423	89.38
7	9:10	51.66	40.18	60.68	75.44	0.08938	1.71462	74.62
8	9:20	41	36.9	46.74	68.06	0.0902	1.66624	63.14
9	9:30	36.9	31.98	41.82	58.22	0.09676	1.5375	65.6
10	9:40	31.16	30.34	33.62	54.94	0.09758	1.65394	69.7
11	9:50	33.62	29.52	35.26	57.4	0.1066	2.87246	72.16
12	10:00	36.9	32.8	41.82	55.76	0.1066	2.80276	72.16
13	10:10	31.16	27.88	33.62	54.94	0.10824	2.76504	72.16
14	10:20	27.06	40.18	30.34	77.08	0.11726	2.4108	72.98
15	10:30	27.06	28.7	30.34	57.4	0.10988	2.70436	67.24
16	10:40	54.12	84.46	63.96	128.74	0.11398	1.79826	68.06
17	10:50	27.06	27.88	30.34	63.14	0.09512	1.0373	60.68
18	11:00	32.8	26.24	34.44	54.94	0.0943	1.18326	60.68

19	11:10	24.6	31.98	28.7	62.32	0.10742	1.50224	65.6
20	11:20	23.78	27.06	27.88	51.66	0.12546	1.29642	72.98
21	11:30	23.78	31.16	27.88	59.86	0.10906	1.8573	61.5
22	11:40	21.32	25.42	24.6	53.3	0.10086	0.77326	59.04
23	11:50	89.38	25.42	112.34	53.3	0.11562	0.77326	65.6
24	12:00	77.08	31.16	95.94	57.4	0.11234	1.93356	63.96
25	12:10	24.6	24.6	28.7	43.46	0.10086	1.49978	55.76
26	12:20	21.32	19.68	24.6	36.9	0.12054	1.47846	64.78
27	12:30	16.4	20.5	18.86	39.36	0.10086	1.05698	55.76
28	12:40	21.32	28.7	24.6	45.92	0.10414	1.39154	59.04
29	12:50	15.58	19.68	18.04	36.9	0.10086	1.36694	59.04
30	1:00	20.5	28.7	23.78	50.84	0.08938	1.76874	54.94
31	1:10	16.4	8.2	18.86	27.06	0.09102	0.97088	54.94
32	1:20	18.86	28.7	21.32	51.66	0.10742	1.66296	61.5
33	1:30	16.4	19.68	18.86	31.16	0.09512	2.2058	58.22
34	1:40	68.88	68.88	84.46	113.16	0.1271	2.14266	69.7
35	1:50	20.5	27.06	23.78	55.76	0.10168	0.8487	52.48
36	2:00	16.4	22.96	18.86	41	0.09922	0.71832	53.3
37	2:10	16.4	22.14	18.86	40.18	0.0902	0.32718	46.74
38	2:20	15.58	27.88	18.04	51.66	0.0861	0.57236	44.28
39	2:30	19.68	36.9	22.96	64.78	0.10168	0.88068	52.48
40	2:40	23.78	24.6	27.88	45.1	0.08692	0.29602	45.92
41	2:50	13.94	24.6	16.4	50.02	0.08528	0.83148	43.46

42	3:00	18.04	29.52	20.5	54.94	0.10004	1.00204	54.12
43	3:10	27.06	36.9	30.34	63.96	0.10906	2.00982	55.76
44	3:20	54.12	37.72	63.96	71.34	0.11398	1.4514	60.68
45	3:30	14.76	18.04	17.22	38.54	0.08856	0.47888	47.56
46	3:40	16.4	23.78	18.86	50.02	0.08856	0.60106	45.1
47	3:50	16.4	33.62	18.86	63.96	0.8036	1.66542	57.4
48	4:00	13.94	19.68	15.58	38.54	0.6642	0.24272	44.28
49	4:10	14.76	27.88	17.22	54.12	0.697	1.26198	41
50	4:20	15.58	26.24	18.04	50.84	0.08364	1.53586	49.2
51	4:30	14.76	23.78	17.22	40.18	0.07134	0.71258	43.46
52	4:40	16.4	28.7	18.86	52.48	0.0697	1.01926	42.64
53	4:50	19.68	30.34	22.96	59.86	0.07708	1.51782	44.28
54	5:00	13.94	18.86	16.4	33.62	0.0615	0.12054	35.26
55	5:10	18.86	25.42	21.32	49.2	0.07626	0.47396	41.82
56	5:20	16.4	27.06	18.86	52.48	0.07052	0.60926	41.82
57	5:30	15.58	22.96	18.04	41	0.07216	0.2952	41.82
58	5:40	16.4	23.78	18.86	38.54	0.07052	0.45756	42.64
59	5:50	18.86	31.98	22.14	58.22	0.07872	0.89216	45.92
60	6:00	35.26	42.64	36.08	73.8	0.1107	1.9147	78.72
61	6:10	19.68	28.7	22.96	54.94	0.15744	2.22712	109.06
62	6:20	36.9	40.18	41.82	79.54	0.1107	2.21646	76.26
63	6:30	62.32	33.62	75.44	63.96	0.11562	2.2878	81.18
64	6:40	113.16	73.8	143.5	113.16	0.12628	3.68262	86.1

65	6:50	21.32	25.42	31.98	43.46	0.13038	1.6072	83.64
66	7:00	19.68	27.88	22.96	59.04	0.11152	2.64204	75.44
67	7:10	19.68	31.16	22.96	55.76	0.1066	0.82656	72.16
68	7:20	23.78	41	27.88	78.72	0.15006	3.02252	101.68
69	7:30	27.06	27.06	30.34	50.84	0.08282	1.53914	59.04
70	7:40	17.22	24.6	19.68	41	0.0943	0.27552	65.6
71	7:50	31.16	38.54	33.62	74.62	0.10168	1.16112	67.24
72	8:00	28.7	31.98	31.16	64.78	0.09758	1.27264	66.42
	TOTAL	2218.1	2278.78	2602.68	4221.36	9.11676	33.81434	1536.68
DAY								
2								
1	8:10	28.7	30.34	31.16	56.58	0.11152	1.28166	74.62
2	8:20	23.78	31.16	27.88	55.76	0.0943	0.9758	63.96
3	8:30	50.02	51.66	59.86	88.56	0.10824	2.40342	74.62
4	8:40	33.62	28.7	35.26	50.02	0.06888	0.03116	51.66
5	8:50	24.6	28.7	28.7	53.3	0.14432	2.56496	99.22
6	9:00	32.8	37.72	34.44	76.26	0.10086	2.13774	69.7
7	9:10	35.26	40.18	36.08	73.8	0.17876	1.8819	133.66
8	9:20	45.92	41	54.12	78.72	0.09266	1.68838	66.42
9	9:30	58.22	44.28	69.7	75.44	0.11808	4.3255	86.1

10	9:40	20.5	29.52	23.78	55.76	0.07462	0.74128	54.12
11	9:50	18.04	25.42	20.5	44.28	0.07216	0.76752	52.48
12	10:00	16.4	22.14	18.86	39.36	0.06642	0.31898	49.2
13	10:10	43.46	24.6	50.84	49.2	0.09184	1.72118	64.78
14	10:20	21.32	30.34	24.6	56.58	0.06724	0.46084	48.38
15	10:30	14.76	23.78	17.22	43.46	0.06396	0.07052	47.56
16	10:40	15.58	24.6	18.04	41.82	0.0656	0.03854	46.74
17	10:50	15.58	25.42	18.04	50.84	0.1148	1.43828	81.18
18	11:00	15.58	22.96	18.04	40.18	0.09266	1.58752	64.78
19	11:10	17.22	22.14	19.68	40.18	0.09102	0.77736	65.6
20	11:20	15.58	22.96	18.04	36.9	0.07298	0.42476	52.48
21	11:30	16.4	21.32	18.86	37.72	0.06888	0.18286	48.38
22	11:40	16.4	25.42	18.86	44.28	0.06724	1.27838	47.56
23	11:50	13.94	15.58	15.58	30.34	0.06068	0.27716	42.64
24	12:00	15.58	24.6	18.04	42.64	0.06314	0.08692	44.28
25	12:10	58.22	22.96	69.7	42.64	0.06724	0.17876	45.92
26	12:20	15.58	21.32	18.04	41	0.06396	0.164	45.92
27	12:30	14.76	23.78	17.22	41	0.082	0.69208	57.4
28	12:40	15.58	20.5	17.22	40.18	0.06396	0.25256	46.74
29	12:50	15.58	17.22	18.04	31.98	0.0615	0.37392	44.28
30	1:00	13.12	19.68	15.58	31.98	0.06068	0.09922	41.82
31	1:10	13.94	18.86	15.58	30.34	0.06396	0.17794	45.1
32	1:20	13.94	18.86	16.4	38.54	0.06478	0.24354	45.1

33	1:30	62.32	18.86	75.44	36.9	0.06232	0.12792	42.64
34	1:40	15.58	21.32	18.04	39.36	0.08282	0.47314	57.4
35	1:50	13.94	19.68	16.4	34.44	0.06068	0.41738	43.46
36	2:00	15.58	20.5	18.04	39.36	0.07052	0.46658	50.02
37	2:10	13.94	20.5	16.4	36.08	0.06314	0.35998	45.1
38	2:20	13.94	18.04	16.4	38.54	0.07872	0.1804	54.94
39	2:30	13.94	17.22	16.4	26.24	0.06314	0.58302	46.74
40	2:40	19.68	17.22	22.96	37.72	0.06396	0.39442	44.28
41	2:50	13.12	18.86	14.76	31.16	0.05822	0.08036	40.18
42	3:00	13.12	16.4	14.76	26.24	0.06232	0.57482	45.92
43	3:10	18.04	22.14	20.5	39.36	0.07052	0.32226	46.74
44	3:20	13.94	18.04	16.4	42.64	0.07052	0.23944	46.74
45	3:30	15.58	18.04	18.04	32.8	0.09266	1.57768	64.78
46	3:40	13.94	14.76	15.58	31.16	0.0656	0.6642	45.1
47	3:50	13.12	17.22	14.76	30.34	0.05986	0.1968	40.18
48	4:00	16.4	14.76	18.86	28.7	0.08856	0.23042	62.32
49	4:10	13.94	18.86	16.4	35.26	0.05904	0.17794	41
50	4:20	13.94	22.14	15.58	38.54	0.05822	0.1927	38.54
51	4:30	13.94	18.04	15.58	41	0.0574	0.10824	39.36
52	4:40	11.48	18.86	12.3	30.34	0.06314	0.4387	45.92
53	4:50	14.76	17.22	17.22	27.88	0.06642	0.2829	45.92
54	5:00	13.94	16.4	16.4	27.88	0.07134	1.0578	49.2
55	5:10	13.94	18.04	15.58	31.98	0.07544	0.42558	52.48

56	5:20	13.94	15.58	16.4	27.88	0.06806	0.83804	44.28
57	5:30	13.94	22.14	16.4	40.18	0.06068	0.67486	42.64
58	5:40	11.48	14.76	11.48	29.52	0.06314	0.5289	42.64
59	5:50	11.48	14.76	12.3	35.26	0.06806	0.32226	48.38
60	6:00	13.12	13.94	14.76	27.06	0.06068	0.37884	42.64
61	6:10	12.3	14.76	13.94	26.24	0.05904	0.26076	39.36
62	6:20	15.58	14.76	18.04	25.42	0.07052	1.73102	51.66
63	6:30	21.32	24.6	24.6	41	0.06888	1.5949	49.2
64	6:40	43.46	15.58	49.2	27.88	0.0615	0.28946	41
65	6:50	15.58	13.12	17.22	22.96	0.05822	0.9799	43.46
66	7:00	11.48	9.84	12.3	16.4	0.06806	0.71668	47.56
67	7:10	16.4	25.42	18.86	45.1	0.1148	0.861	78.72
68	7:20	14.76	20.5	17.22	36.9	0.06396	0.9102	45.1
69	7:30	18.04	28.7	20.5	54.12	0.06068	0.3485	42.64
70	7:40	13.12	14.76	14.76	26.24	0.05904	0.51332	41
71	7:50	14.76	15.58	17.22	29.52	0.09594	2.22466	68.06
72	8:00	12.3	13.12	13.94	28.7	0.05576	0.2542	40.18
	TOTAL	1425.16	1572.76	1635.9	2883.94	5.40052	52.64482	3799.88
DAY								
3								

1	8:10	82.82	47.56	103.32	86.92	0.1107	0.89298	72.16
2	8:20	54.12	40.18	63.96	75.44	0.10578	1.44484	68.88
3	8:30	51.66	41	60.68	77.9	0.1025	0.17384	69.7
4	8:40	43.46	45.1	50.84	79.54	0.11562	2.65188	80.36
5	8:50	168.92	41.82	218.94	77.08	0.11234	0.82902	77.08
6	9:00	250.1	98.4	337.84	152.52	0.12546	1.85812	87.74
7	9:10	39.36	42.64	45.1	83.64	0.15744	2.38538	94.3
8	9:20	51.66	57.4	60.68	91.84	0.123	3.01432	84.46
9	9:30	43.46	51.66	50.84	88.56	0.12628	3.07254	89.38
10	9:40	28.7	42.64	31.16	77.08	0.10414	1.0783	70.52
11	9:50	31.16	36.9	33.62	65.6	0.7708	0.17548	54.94
12	10:00	37.72	38.54	43.46	68.88	0.082	0.80524	56.58
13	10:10	37.72	41.82	43.46	77.9	0.082	2.09264	56.58
14	10:20	45.1	41	52.48	72.98	0.11398	2.08772	78.72
15	10:30	32.8	37.72	34.44	68.06	0.10578	2.37226	75.44
16	10:40	148.42	180.4	191.06	277.16	0.12874	4.25826	94.3
17	10:50	63.96	100.04	77.08	159.08	0.13366	2.67156	93.48
18	11:00	35.26	48.38	36.9	86.92	0.12382	3.0463	83.64
19	11:10	41	53.3	46.74	88.56	0.12464	4.26892	89.38
20	11:20	77.08	38.54	95.12	74.62	0.12546	5.33656	87.74
21	11:30	45.92	45.92	54.12	81.18	0.4756	2.77898	58.22
22	11:40	43.46	41	50.84	77.08	0.4592	1.48256	57.4
23	11:50	35.26	53.3	36.08	89.38	0.738	5.40216	84.46

24	12:00	69.7	37.72	111.52	64.78	0.6232	1.96718	76.26
25	12:10	31.16	34.44	33.62	56.58	0.5248	2.71256	67.24
26	12:20	36.9	40.18	41.82	71.34	0.5986	2.08362	73.8
27	12:30	66.42	48.38	81.18	88.56	0.5576	2.66992	71.34
28	12:40	41	47.56	46.74	86.92	0.615	2.64696	67.24
29	12:50	28.7	33.62	31.16	71.34	0.5166	0.85772	65.6
30	1:00	35.26	34.44	36.08	65.6	0.615	1.7302	77.08
31	1:10	33.62	36.9	35.26	67.24	0.738	1.97128	92.66
32	1:20	27.06	33.62	30.34	63.14	0.492	2.44442	62.32
33	1:30	24.6	34.44	28.7	63.96	0.656	1.72528	77.08
34	1:40	34.44	44.28	54.94	76.26	0.6068	2.46328	73.8
35	1:50	33.62	37.72	35.26	75.44	0.492	2.02048	65.6
36	2:00	39.36	41	45.1	76.26	0.5166	1.5088	67.24
37	2:10	37.72	52.48	43.46	87.74	0.615	3.17996	77.08
38	2:20	37.72	39.36	43.46	77.08	0.5576	2.87082	70.52
39	2:30	105.78	33.62	134.48	61.5	0.656	1.4678	86.1
40	2:40	77.08	71.34	95.94	117.26	0.5658	2.05984	71.34
41	2:50	31.16	33.62	33.62	61.5	0.5494	1.06026	71.34
42	3:00	35.26	40.18	36.9	72.16	0.5412	1.33906	71.34
43	3:10	41.82	43.46	47.56	79.54	0.6314	3.48828	77.08
44	3:20	91.02	166.46	113.98	243.54	0.5248	3.78758	68.06
45	3:30	28.7	36.9	31.16	69.7	0.6478	3.20374	84.46
46	3:40	23.78	33.62	27.88	63.14	0.451	2.54036	61.5

47	3:50	24.6	31.98	28.7	63.96	0.5412	2.25008	70.52
48	4:00	62.32	62.32	74.62	95.94	0.533	2.82162	72.16
49	4:10	39.36	35.26	45.1	63.96	0.5412	1.71298	70.52
50	4:20	22.96	31.98	27.06	36.9	0.4838	2.13938	66.42
51	4:30	28.7	37.72	31.16	68.88	0.5166	1.66952	68.88
52	4:40	28.7	56.58	31.16	90.2	0.5576	2.51904	72.98
53	4:50	23.78	33.62	27.88	60.68	0.5002	2.05246	63.96
54	5:00	20.5	29.52	24.6	53.3	0.5166	1.24394	69.7
55	5:10	22.14	32.8	25.42	61.5	0.6068	1.7302	82
56	5:20	20.5	33.62	23.78	62.32	0.5002	2.0131	66.42
57	5:30	24.6	31.16	28.7	55.76	0.5658	1.5539	77.08
58	5:40	31.98	34.44	42.64	71.34	0.16564	2.03196	113.98
59	5:50	68.88	132.02	84.46	207.46	0.5658	4.81668	77.08
60	6:00	31.16	32.8	33.62	57.4	0.4428	2.1689	60.68
61	6:10	18.04	27.88	20.5	50.02	0.4592	2.50346	63.96
62	6:20	36.9	50.84	41.82	86.92	0.4264	2.66746	61.5
63	6:30	23.78	29.52	27.88	54.94	0.4428	2.6896	62.32
64	6:40	95.12	32.8	119.72	59.04	0.5822	1.558	77.9
65	6:50	22.96	32.8	27.06	55.76	0.4756	1.58096	67.24
66	7:00	22.96	38.54	27.06	68.88	0.6478	4.03276	89.38
67	7:10	47.56	144.32	54.94	226.32	0.5494	4.59938	70.52
68	7:20	19.68	27.06	22.96	50.84	0.7872	0.369	81.18
69	7:30	28.7	36.08	31.16	70.52	0.41	1.45058	59.04

70	7:40	22.96	34.44	26.24	63.14	0.08364	2.83884	112.34
71	7:50	21.32	28.7	24.6	53.3	0.4592	1.7384	63.14
72	8:00	13.94	19.68	16.4	35.26	0.5248	0.30586	70.52
	TOTAL	799.5	1086.5	940.54	5963.04	12.34428	54.80798	1840.9
DAY								
4								
1	8:10	21.32	67.24	24.6	104.96	0.11562	1.4104	74.62
2	8:20	15.58	24.6	18.04	41	0.10004	1.03976	64.78
3	8:30	105.78	61.5	134.48	98.4	0.1189	4.31976	75.44
4	8:40	27.06	44.28	30.34	81.18	0.12628	2.43704	81.18
5	8:50	19.68	36.08	22.96	66.42	0.13858	3.32264	90.2
6	9:00	35.26	40.18	36.08	74.62	0.13366	2.12052	86.1
7	9:10	35.26	35.26	36.08	67.24	0.14022	2.56414	91.84
8	9:20	36.9	42.64	41.82	88.56	0.10988	1.44976	71.34
9	9:30	28.7	34.44	31.16	68.88	0.123	3.19472	81.18
10	9:40	21.32	31.16	24.6	57.4	0.13284	1.77612	86.1
11	9:50	36.9	50.02	41.82	91.02	0.09594	1.63508	62.32
12	10:00	17.22	31.16	19.68	53.3	0.11316	1.148	73.8
13	10:10	15.58	31.16	18.86	55.76	0.11808	1.0947	78.72
14	10:20	21.32	35.26	24.6	63.14	0.09348	0.82656	61.5

15	10:30	29.52	26.24	32.8	49.2	0.0984	0.60024	63.96
16	10:40	16.4	27.88	18.86	56.58	0.10906	0.82902	68.88
17	10:50	21.32	31.98	24.6	60.68	0.13038	2.60514	85.28
18	11:00	16.4	24.6	18.86	42.64	0.12874	0.68388	83.64
19	11:10	16.4	27.06	18.86	53.3	0.12874	2.42638	83.64
20	11:20	27.06	41	30.34	71.34	0.11316	2.2017	72.98
21	11:30	17.22	24.6	19.68	41.82	0.09512	0.67568	61.5
22	11:40	51.66	56.58	60.68	97.58	0.11808	2.84704	77.08
23	11:50	92.66	167.28	115.62	273.88	0.13776	4.32796	94.3
24	12:00	20.5	39.36	23.78	72.16	0.10988	1.8491	69.7
25	12:10	22.14	26.24	25.42	52.48	0.1189	1.68018	79.54
26	12:20	15.58	30.34	18.04	67.24	0.10906	0.96186	69.7
27	12:30	16.4	34.44	18.86	59.86	0.10906	1.54734	67.24
28	12:40	13.94	26.24	16.4	57.4	0.0984	1.66952	62.32
29	12:50	19.68	23.78	22.96	47.56	0.12136	1.0701	79.54
30	1:00	15.58	22.14	18.04	45.92	0.11398	1.34234	72.98
31	1:10	13.94	22.96	16.4	37.72	0.09184	0.89544	59.04
32	1:20	14.76	27.88	17.22	53.3	0.10496	1.67198	67.24
33	1:30	15.58	51.66	18.04	89.38	0.09512	1.2136	62.32
34	1:40	13.12	18.86	14.76	30.34	0.10578	0.60188	63.96
35	1:50	17.22	34.44	19.68	64.78	0.1025	1.04796	65.6
36	2:00	43.46	54.12	49.2	118.08	0.11562	2.65024	75.44
37	2:10	32.8	44.28	34.44	83.64	0.10988	1.2341	70.52

38	2:20	13.94	25.42	16.4	49.2	0.1107	0.93398	72.98
39	2:30	15.58	22.96	18.04	41.82	0.14432	1.50142	95.12
40	2:40	41.82	78.72	47.56	136.12	0.0984	0.89134	63.14
41	2:50	47.56	50.02	54.94	86.1	0.10004	1.45222	64.78
42	3:00	24.6	38.54	28.7	72.98	0.1107	2.43212	69.7
43	3:10	16.4	25.42	18.86	49.2	0.09922	0.5863	63.96
44	3:20	16.4	22.14	18.86	54.12	0.09266	0.44772	59.04
45	3:30	13.12	19.68	14.76	36.9	0.08938	0.6273	56.58
46	3:40	77.08	45.92	95.94	80.36	0.1148	1.28412	69.7
47	3:50	15.58	22.14	18.04	39.36	0.10988	0.54366	69.7
48	4:00	15.58	27.88	18.04	53.3	0.10824	1.35218	66.42
49	4:10	18.04	31.98	20.5	60.68	0.10824	1.33578	69.7
50	4:20	16.4	28.7	18.86	53.3	0.10168	1.52192	63.96
51	4:30	23.78	35.26	27.88	71.34	0.1148	1.77202	74.62
52	4:40	13.94	19.68	15.58	34.44	0.11316	1.0291	69.7
53	4:50	14.76	19.68	17.22	39.36	0.08774	0.54284	54.94
54	5:00	13.12	22.96	14.76	39.36	0.10824	0.73882	66.42
55	5:10	13.94	21.32	16.4	38.54	0.0902	0.62648	56.58
56	5:20	13.94	24.6	16.4	49.2	0.11234	1.3899	70.52
57	5:30	13.12	17.22	14.76	29.52	0.08856	0.53054	55.76
58	5:40	15.58	30.34	18.04	55.76	0.0984	0.70356	63.96
59	5:50	15.58	26.24	18.04	45.1	0.09594	1.57686	60.68
60	6:00	13.12	18.86	14.76	31.16	0.10578	1.73266	62.32

61	6:10	15.58	25.42	18.04	50.02	0.09594	2.18366	59.04
62	6:20	13.12	19.68	14.76	29.52	0.0984	1.02664	60.68
63	6:30	13.12	18.86	14.76	31.16	0.10496	2.0131	63.96
64	6:40	13.12	17.22	14.76	38.54	0.1066	0.99302	65.6
65	6:50	13.94	18.86	16.4	36.9	0.0861	0.53382	54.94
66	7:00	16.4	33.62	18.86	61.5	0.09184	1.04058	59.04
67	7:10	27.06	36.9	30.34	53.3	0.1271	2.08936	82.82
68	7:20	15.58	27.06	18.04	44.28	0.12546	2.747	79.54
69	7:30	15.58	36.08	18.04	72.98	0.09266	1.14472	59.86
70	7:40	13.12	19.68	14.76	31.16	0.11562	3.06434	73.8
71	7:50	65.6	38.54	78.72	73.8	0.10086	2.51904	64.78
72	8:00	20.5	36.9	23.78	67.24	0.09102	1.45714	55.76
	TOTAL	1726.92	2453.44	2003.26	4476.38	7.86544	111.3371	5035.62
DAY								
5								
1	8:10	29.52	40.18	32.8	74.62	0.11152	2.39604	72.98
2	8:20	50.84	63.14	60.68	106.6	0.09512	5.24308	67.24
3	8:30	245.18	71.34	328.82	106.6	0.10168	1.28166	69.7
4	8:40	27.06	54.94	30.34	95.12	0.0861	1.52028	62.32
5	8:50	13.12	20.5	14.76	29.52	0.08692	3.79168	59.86

6	9:00	16.4	32.8	18.86	61.5	0.09922	2.08362	69.7
7	9:10	16.4	29.52	18.86	52.48	0.09594	1.20048	67.24
8	9:20	16.4	26.24	18.86	50.84	0.082	0.79048	56.58
9	9:30	16.4	39.36	18.86	68.06	0.10332	2.04836	68.06
10	9:40	39.36	46.74	45.1	81.18	0.11398	2.44934	78.72
11	9:50	54.88	27.88	100	51.66	0.1066	0.96924	73.8
12	10:00	20.5	39.36	23.78	71.34	0.11972	2.57726	83.64
13	10:10	16.4	28.7	18.86	54.12	0.09348	1.95734	63.14
14	10:20	16.4	27.88	18.86	47.56	0.5658	1.32266	55.76
15	10:30	15.58	27.88	18.04	41	0.5494	1.51044	54.12
16	10:40	16.4	40.18	18.86	70.52	0.5658	1.01106	56.58
17	10:50	14.76	27.88	17.22	42.64	0.7626	1.4637	72.16
18	11:00	13.12	17.22	14.76	29.52	0.615	0.82164	63.14
19	11:10	15.58	31.16	18.04	58.22	0.7954	2.73716	78.72
20	11:20	21.32	22.14	29.52	37.72	0.0861	1.54816	84.46
21	11:30	21.32	34.44	24.6	63.14	0.574	1.20458	59.04
22	11:40	15.58	25.42	18.04	38.54	0.5002	1.00204	51.66
23	11:50	68.88	41	84.46	73.8	0.6724	1.02008	66.42
24	12:00	14.76	31.98	17.22	51.66	0.6068	1.0086	63.96
25	12:10	13.12	22.96	14.76	38.54	0.6642	1.22262	67.24
26	12:20	13.12	20.5	14.76	33.62	0.5986	2.1402	59.86
27	12:30	32.8	29.52	34.44	49.2	0.7298	3.08976	72.98
28	12:40	25.42	42.64	29.52	77.08	0.6724	2.72568	69.7

29	12:50	25.42	68.06	29.52	125.46	0.5822	0.67486	60.68
30	1:00	15.58	30.34	18.04	53.3	0.6068	2.0049	63.96
31	1:10	21.32	35.26	24.6	63.14	0.5986	1.48092	58.22
32	1:20	13.94	26.24	16.4	49.2	0.5986	0.53792	59.86
33	1:30	15.58	29.52	18.04	51.66	0.08364	1.8204	82
34	1:40	16.4	27.88	18.86	50.02	0.574	0.88232	61.5
35	1:50	16.4	28.7	18.86	50.84	0.533	1.517	56.58
36	2:00	21.32	35.26	24.6	65.6	0.6478	1.74414	64.78
37	2:10	32.8	82.82	34.44	134.48	0.5986	3.1242	60.68
38	2:20	15.58	27.06	18.04	44.28	0.7298	1.31692	72.98
39	2:30	18.86	29.52	22.14	54.12	0.7134	1.07338	71.34
40	2:40	31.16	34.44	33.62	62.32	0.7626	2.74208	73.8
41	2:50	18.04	30.34	20.5	53.3	0.5248	0.89462	54.94
42	3:00	23.78	31.98	27.88	63.14	0.6314	1.59162	63.96
43	3:10	20.5	33.62	23.78	55.76	0.6888	1.87288	70.52
44	3:20	14.76	27.06	17.22	45.1	0.6232	0.53546	63.96
45	3:30	15.58	33.62	18.04	61.5	0.6068	1.49404	63.96
46	3:40	21.32	24.6	24.6	43.46	0.5166	2.71994	54.94
47	3:50	36.9	41.82	41.82	75.44	0.6478	2.5215	70.52
48	4:00	74.62	67.24	91.84	112.34	0.6724	2.091	68.88
49	4:10	11.48	14.76	11.48	25.42	0.533	0.7626	54.12
50	4:20	18.04	26.24	20.5	46.74	0.8036	1.66542	82
51	4:30	11.48	18.04	12.3	27.88	0.6232	1.96554	64.78

52	4:40	15.58	18.04	18.04	27.88	0.5904	0.72734	61.5
53	4:50	11.48	22.14	12.3	34.44	0.656	1.17014	70.52
54	5:00	72.16	30.34	88.56	51.66	0.492	1.23	53.3
55	5:10	31.16	72.98	33.62	109.06	0.6396	1.5662	65.6
56	5:20	13.94	21.32	16.4	36.9	0.5904	1.62442	60.68
57	5:30	15.58	21.32	18.04	38.54	0.5986	3.41776	63.14
58	5:40	18.04	25.42	20.5	45.1	0.7954	2.06804	81.18
59	5:50	33.62	17.22	63.96	29.52	0.7216	0.50594	75.44
60	6:00	13.12	18.86	14.76	28.7	0.6642	1.5867	69.7
61	6:10	55.76	27.88	67.24	45.92	0.5576	0.78228	57.4
62	6:20	12.3	18.04	13.94	27.88	0.5494	0.98974	59.04
63	6:30	107.42	69.7	136.12	113.98	0.08446	1.54652	85.28
64	6:40	24.6	38.54	28.7	68.88	0.7298	2.49772	74.62
65	6:50	13.12	27.06	14.76	45.92	0.697	4.41734	72.16
66	7:00	13.12	20.5	14.76	28.7	0.5084	0.96104	55.76
67	7:10	31.16	72.16	33.62	109.06	0.738	2.86918	77.08
68	7:20	55.76	41.82	65.6	73.8	0.533	0.56498	58.22
69	7:30	18.86	24.6	21.32	39.36	0.6068	1.15374	64.78
70	7:40	15.58	25.42	18.04	45.1	0.7462	3.40136	77.9
71	7:50	16.4	34.44	18.86	63.96	0.5576	1.927	59.86
72	8:00	39.36	52.48	45.1	85.28	0.697	1.73512	71.34
	TOTAL	2493.62	2468.2	3160.28	4220.54	36.9082	125.9135	4782.24

DAY								
6								
1	8:10	41	36.08	46.74	73.8	0.10414	0.67158	64.78
2	8:20	19.68	28.7	22.96	50.84	0.12546	0.246	79.54
3	8:30	27.06	31.16	30.34	63.14	0.10004	0.55596	61.5
4	8:40	19.68	29.52	22.96	59.86	0.12218	1.88682	77.08
5	8:50	25.42	29.52	29.52	52.48	0.09512	0.94546	61.5
6	9:00	21.32	30.34	24.6	54.12	0.10086	1.00696	63.96
7	9:10	16.4	26.24	18.86	50.84	0.09922	1.44812	61.5
8	9:20	13.12	22.96	14.76	38.54	0.7708	0.1271	51.66
9	9:30	15.58	20.5	18.04	33.62	0.7872	0.41492	51.66
10	9:40	16.4	22.96	18.86	43.46	0.7872	0.30996	50.84
11	9:50	18.04	29.52	20.5	54.94	0.12628	2.63548	79.54
12	10:00	23.78	25.42	27.88	50.02	0.10906	1.85812	67.24
13	10:10	18.04	27.88	20.5	54.12	0.0861	1.15538	57.4
14	10:20	21.32	28.7	24.6	52.48	0.09676	1.02008	63.96
15	10:30	31.16	30.34	33.62	65.6	0.11234	1.96144	72.98
16	10:40	18.86	26.24	21.32	44.28	0.10578	0.90118	68.06
17	10:50	18.86	33.62	22.14	63.96	0.10332	2.87738	66.42
18	11:00	27.06	36.9	30.34	66.42	0.13284	2.61826	88.56
19	11:10	37.72	37.72	43.46	77.9	0.13612	2.96512	89.38

20	11:20	21.32	30.34	24.6	60.68	0.10004	1.45632	63.96
21	11:30	119.72	66.42	151.7	108.24	0.13694	2.54856	91.02
22	11:40	22.96	41.82	26.24	81.18	0.1025	2.11396	67.24
23	11:50	22.96	38.54	26.24	67.24	0.14596	2.95938	97.58
24	12:00	28.7	41	31.16	76.26	0.1107	1.85566	72.16
25	12:10	22.14	37.72	25.42	74.62	0.14678	2.58054	96.76
26	12:20	32.8	41	34.44	77.9	0.10496	1.58424	68.88
27	12:30	100.86	149.24	127.1	224.68	0.13038	2.4518	86.92
28	12:40	17.22	36.08	29.52	67.24	0.11726	2.0377	77.08
29	12:50	31.16	36.9	33.62	72.98	0.11726	2.72896	79.54
30	1:00	32.8	36.08	34.44	68.06	0.1066	1.9721	68.88
31	1:10	58.22	46.74	69.7	86.92	0.12382	2.54774	81.18
32	1:20	25.42	45.92	29.52	79.54	0.12464	2.95938	83.64
33	1:30	17.22	30.34	19.68	61.5	0.09594	1.15866	65.6
34	1:40	16.4	30.34	18.86	57.4	0.10906	2.4272	72.98
35	1:50	17.22	27.88	19.68	50.84	0.09676	0.81754	63.96
36	2:00	18.04	33.62	20.5	77.08	0.10168	2.18694	66.42
37	2:10	18.04	31.98	20.5	63.96	0.12464	1.24312	82.82
38	2:20	36.9	74.62	41.82	118.08	0.12054	4.13362	78.72
39	2:30	21.32	31.98	24.6	59.86	0.1066	1.78268	68.88
40	2:40	12.3	27.06	19.68	50.84	0.13448	1.4022	88.56
41	2:50	15.58	30.34	18.04	56.58	0.09922	1.1603	64.78
42	3:00	18.86	30.34	21.32	54.94	0.123	1.6236	82.82

43	3:10	17.22	34.44	19.68	65.6	0.11562	1.66378	77.9
44	3:20	15.58	25.42	18.04	42.64	0.08692	1.26034	56.58
45	3:30	15.58	26.24	18.04	51.66	0.10168	1.353	68.06
46	3:40	92.66	113.16	115.62	183.68	0.11726	3.35216	77.9
47	3:50	15.58	26.24	18.04	50.84	0.11234	1.2997	73.8
48	4:00	16.4	24.6	18.86	41.82	0.10086	1.45222	65.6
49	4:10	14.76	27.06	17.22	47.56	0.11234	1.7015	72.98
50	4:20	13.94	24.6	16.4	48.38	0.1066	1.46698	68.88
51	4:30	15.58	26.24	18.04	43.46	0.0902	0.40918	57.4
52	4:40	15.58	26.24	18.04	55.76	0.09266	1.04878	59.04
53	4:50	23.78	39.36	27.88	69.7	0.11152	2.296	72.98
54	5:00	25.42	36.9	29.52	65.6	0.12628	2.05984	85.28
55	5:10	18.86	31.16	22.14	54.94	0.10988	2.28862	72.98
56	5:20	16.4	29.52	18.86	54.94	0.11316	1.96144	76.26
57	5:30	16.4	27.06	18.86	49.2	0.7954	0.32226	52.48
58	5:40	21.32	34.44	24.6	59.04	0.09676	0.76588	66.42
59	5:50	22.96	35.26	27.06	63.96	0.12054	2.14266	79.54
60	6:00	23.78	30.34	27.88	54.94	0.09594	0.89462	63.96
61	6:10	18.04	27.88	20.5	54.94	0.0943	0.67158	62.32
62	6:20	17.22	27.88	19.68	50.02	0.10496	1.14308	70.52
63	6:30	37.72	51.66	43.46	86.1	0.1271	1.24722	85.28
64	6:40	31.16	41.82	33.62	77.9	0.09348	0.60106	63.14
65	6:50	18.04	27.88	20.5	49.2	0.7052	0.02214	48.38

66	7:00	41.82	39.36	47.56	76.26	0.09594	1.84008	63.14
67	7:10	55.76	39.36	67.24	77.9	0.11316	1.72036	75.44
68	7:20	19.68	37.72	22.96	71.34	0.08774	1.71134	57.4
69	7:30	18.04	28.7	20.5	54.12	0.09594	1.47436	62.32
70	7:40	23.78	35.26	27.88	67.24	0.0984	1.52028	66.42
71	7:50	23.78	25.42	27.88	41.82	0.7872	0.4305	50.84
72	8:00	36.9	115.62	41.82	170.56	0.10906	2.60432	70.52
	TOTAL	587.12	891.34	3522.72	4828.16	11.89902	116.0628	5071.7